

Quantity-Intensity Relation of Potassium in Soils of Selected Land-uses in the Humid Rainforest Agroecology, Southeastern, Nigeria

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Abstract

Application of Q/I concept constitutes a viable approach for the estimation of soil K status and crop K requirements. Soil samples were collected from the 0-15 and 15-30 cm depths of oil palm, cassava, plantain and sycamore land-uses in the humid rainforest agroecology, Southeastern Nigeria and analyzed for K forms and Q/I parameters. Data generated for the K forms and the Q/I parameters were subjected to ANOVA and means separated using LSD at 5% probability level. Also, the K forms were correlated with soil properties and K Q/I parameters and equally amongst themselves using correlation analysis. Potassium forms significantly (LSD 0.05) decreased as total > structural > available > exchangeable > non-exchangeable > solution K. The K Q/I parameters varied significantly (LSD_{0.05}) according to land-uses and soil depths and ranged between 1.16-2.03 Mol L^{-1/2} x 10⁻³ (AR_e^{ok}), 9.25-17.75 cmol kg⁻¹ (K_L), 3.63-6.13 cmol kg⁻¹ (K_o), 5.63-12.25 cmol kg⁻¹ (K_x), 6.37-9.81 cmol kg⁻¹ (mol L⁻¹)^{-1/2} (PBC^{ok}), 26.14-53.96 cmol kg⁻¹ (mol L⁻¹)^{-1/2} (K_{pot}), 0.82-1.83 L mol⁻¹)^{-1/2} (K_G), 328.32-1562.82 KJ mol⁻¹ (-ΔG) and 0.14-0.50% (K_{sat}). Whereas the inter-correlation of K forms was significant (P < 0.05), the correlation between K Q/I parameters with most K forms and soil properties and between K forms with most soil properties were distinct. The Q/I concept could be useful for understanding of transformation of K in soil and the prediction of K fertilizer for sustained crop performance.

Keywords: potassium, Q/I relationship, land-use, humid rainforest and Nigeria.

Introduction

Potassium is a primary macronutrient that is essential for physiological processes of water and assimilates transport, stomata opening and enzyme activation as well as carbohydrate synthesis and nutrient utilization by plants (Yawson et al., 2011; Uzoho et al., 2016). It exists in four forms in the soil as solution, exchangeable, non-exchangeable and lattice/structural K each of which is in direct equilibrium with the other (Spark et al., 1990). Solution K constitutes the fraction that is

readily available in the immediate soil solution and easily lost via uptake or leaching, exchangeable K consists the labile K pool in the soil solid that is readily released into solution as it is depleted, non-exchangeable K constitutes the non readily available K fraction that is usually associated with soil organic matter and clay fractions while structural/lattice K is the form associated with clay minerals and released during mineral weathering (Yawson et al., 2011).

Soil K status or concentration varies depending on K forms, labile pool in the soil solid phase, amount in soil solution and the rate at which K is released from the labile pool into the solution phase (Bangroo et al., 2020). Availability of soil K and its plant requirement is estimated using exchangeable K obtained with neutral 1 N NH_4OAC salt solution (Hamed and Amin, 2017; Panda and Patra, 2018) with values often misleading and unsatisfactory (Al-Zubaidi and Yanni, 2008). This could be due to the complexity of soil K release and fixation dynamics, poor ability of extractants to explain nutrient uptake and the inability to assess dynamic interactions amongst K pools that determines the availability (Anthony et al., 2013; Nongqenda and Modi, 2016; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). Another method, the thermodynamic approach involving K quantity-intensity concept has recently been widely used in the understanding, characterizing and evaluation of soil K supplying capacity (Yawson et al., 2011; Lalitha and Dharkshinamoorthy, 2015; Biliias and Barbayiannis, 2019). This approach supposes that K concentration in soils depends on the total amount present in readily available form in the soil solid (quantity factor) and the intensity (intensity factor) with which it is released into soil solution. The intensity factor is expressed as the activity ratio of K with Ca and Mg computed using the relation; Activity ratio (AR) = $a\text{K}/a(\text{Ca} + \text{Mg})^{1/2}$ (Beckett, 1964). A plot of Q/I yields isotherm whose parameters help in estimation of soil K availability. These parameters include the K activity ratio ($\text{AR}_e^{\text{K}0}$) at equilibrium solution concentration (a measure of immediate K availability in solution), labile K (K_L) or available K that is capable of ion exchange, non-specific site K (K_o) (a measure of K held non specifically on planar surface exchange sites), specific K (K_X) (fixed K adsorbed with high affinity at wedge sites of clay minerals), potential buffering capacity (PBC) (a measure of the ability to maintain soil solution K concentration), energy of K replacement ($-\Delta G$) (the amount of energy required to take up K from the soil) and the Gapon selectivity coefficient (k_G) (a measure of the affinity with which K is held in the soil in the presence of Ca and Mg) (Sharma et al., 2012; Panda and Patra, 2018).

Potassium availability or Q/I parameters is affected by land-use types. This could be due to changes in soil properties, K forms, landscape positions and soil types (Kulhanek et al., 2008; Abaslou and Abtahi, 2008; Sharma et al., 2012; Panda and Patra, 2018; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). For instance, correlations between Q/I parameters with soil properties and K forms have been reported for marginal soils under guava land-use (Sharma et al., 2012) and alluvial soils under varying cropping systems (Lalitha and Dhakshinamoorthy, 2015).

In Nigeria, soils of the humid rainforest region are characterized by widespread K deficiencies due to leaching and erosion by the intense rainfall (Uzoho and Jaja, 2018). Currently, information regarding the use of Q/I relationship for evaluation of K status of these soils is limited. Understanding the K dynamics of these soils would help provide insight into their K transformations and useful for sustained K management under different land-uses. The objective of this present study was therefore to determine the K status of soils of selected land-uses using the Q/I concept and their correlation with selected soil properties.

Materials and Methods

Study Location

The study location was Awka-Etiti, Idemili LGA, Anambra state on Latitudes $6^{\circ}12^1$ and $6^{\circ}37^1$ N and Longitudes $7^{\circ} 4^1$ and $7^{\circ} 23^1$ E and elevation of 116 mm above sea level. The mean annual rainfall ranges between 2015-2020 mm with a binomial pattern that peaks in the months of July and September and a short dry spell, the August break in the month of August. Its mean daily temperature ranges between 26-30°C and with a mean relative humidity of 78-85%. The soil types consist of Ruptic Paleodult and Arenic Kandidult (Soil Survey staff, 2017) derived from Coastal Plain Sands (Orajiaka, 1975). Main economic activities of the area include farming, trading, fishing, artisanry and civil service. The climax vegetations varied depending on the land-use types.

Sample Collections and Preparations

Triplicate soil samples were collected from two depths; topsoil (0-15cm) and subsoil (15-30 cm) of Oil palm, Cassava, Plantain and Sycamore land-uses. Samples from 0-15 and 15-30 cm depths respectively were denoted as soils number 1&2 (Oil palm), 3&4 (Cassava), 5 & 6 (plantain) and 7 & 8 (sycamore). The Oil palm land-use consisted of more than 25 years old palm plantation previously fertilized using inorganic fertilizers especially N and K fertilizers and underlain with Calapogonium cover crop, the cassava was a one and half year old farm fertilized with inorganic fertilizers (NPKS 12:12:17: 5), plantain land-use was a three to five years old homestead farm fertilized using house-hold refuse while the sycamore was more than four years old sycamore trees planted in a church premises. In each land-use, soil samples from the same depths were bulked to obtain a composite which were air dried, crushed and sieved using a 2 mm diameter sieve and the fine earth fractions obtained stored ready for laboratory analyses.

Laboratory Analyses

The fine earth soil samples were analyzed for particle size distribution after dispersion with calgon (Gee and Or, 2002), exchangeable cations and ECEC (Thomas, 1996), pH in 1:2.5 soil/water ratio using glass electrode of the pH meter, organic matter (Nelson and Sommers, 1996), available P (Olsen and Sommers, 1982) and total N (Bremner, 1996). Also, K forms were determined as; water soluble K (Grewal and Kanwar, 1966), available K using 1 N NH_4OAC (Jackson, 1973), exchangeable K as the difference between available and water soluble K, non-exchangeable K using boiling HNO_3 (Wood and Deturk, 1940), lattice/structural/mineral K as a difference of the summation of non-exchangeable and available K from total K (Wiklander, 1954) while total K was determined after extraction with HF-HClO_4 (Black 1965). The various potassium fractions were determined using the flame photometer. Percentage K saturation of the various soil samples was calculated as;

$$\% K \text{ saturation} = \frac{K_{\text{adsorbed}}(\text{cmol kg}^{-1})}{\text{ECEC}(\text{cmol kg}^{-1})} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Potassium Quantity-Intensity Relationship

Quantity-intensity K relationship was determined by adding 50 ml of 0.01M CaCl_2 solution containing graded concentrations of K (0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 mmol L^{-1}) as KCL into 5 g soil samples in centrifugation bottles (Beckett, 1964). The soil suspensions were shaken vigorously for 2 hrs and allowed to equilibrate overnight before centrifugation. The soil suspensions were then

filtered and aliquots of the clear supernatants analyzed for K using a flame photometer while exchangeable Ca and Mg were determined by EDTA versenate titration (Carter and Gregorich, 2008). Adsorbed or change in K (ΔK) concentration was obtained as the difference between added K and equilibrium solution K. The K intensity factor (I) or activity ratio (AR^K) was obtained using the relation;

$$AR^K = a_K (a_{Ca+Mg})^{-1/2} = C_K (C_{Ca+Mg})^{-1/2} \times f_K (f_{Ca+Mg})^{-1/2}, \text{ where;}$$

AR^K = the activity ratio of K^+ to Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} after equilibration (mol L^{-1})^{1/2},

a_K = activity of K^+ (mol L^{-1}),

$a_{(Ca+Mg)}$ = activity of $Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}$ (mol L^{-1}),

f_K = activity coefficient of K, f_{Ca+Mg} = activity coefficient of $Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}$.

For a 0.01M $CaCl_2$ dilute solution, the activity coefficient ratio of $f_K/f_{(Ca+Mg)}$ ^{1/2} is closer to unity as the values vary very little within the range of K^+ and $Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}$ concentrations used in the equilibrium solutions (Wang, 1988). Thus, the concentration of K^+ in equilibrium solution was assumed as the activity ratio of the ions i.e $AR^K = C_K (C_{Ca} + C_{Mg})^{-1/2}$.

Change in K ($\pm \Delta K$) or quantity factor (Q) was plotted on the ordinate against the activity ratio (AR^K) or intensity factor (I) on the abscissa to obtain the K Q/I isotherm. The intercept of the isotherm on the AR axis at zero level of $\pm \Delta K$ represented the equilibrium activity ratio of K^+ (AR_e^{ok}) or soil solution K^+ activity relative to $Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}$ at equilibrium. The linear portion of the curve was extrapolated to the ordinate by drawing a tangent from the point of the abscissa where $\pm \Delta K = 0$ to obtain the readily exchangeable K^+ held on the planar sites or non specific edges (K_o). The low curvature at lower values of AR_e^K was as a result of the release of fixed K^+ from the soil particles, with the intercept representing K at specific sites with high K affinity (K_x). Also, the amount of ΔK at $AR_e^K = 0$ indicated the quantity of total pool of labile K (K_L) in the soil ($K_o + K_x$) and signified the amount of readily available K which is capable of ion exchange during the period of equilibrium between the soil colloids and soil solution. The potential buffering capacity of K (PBC^K) was calculated as the slope of $\Delta K / AR_e^K$ of the linear portion of the curve and constitutes a measure of the ability of the soil to maintain the intensity of K^+ in the soil solution. Also, K^+ potential of the soil was obtained by multiplying K_o with the PBC^K (Dutta and Joshi, 1990) while the free energy of K replacement ($-\Delta G$) was computed using the relation $\Delta G = 2.303RT \log AR^{ok}$ (Beckett, 1964), where, R and K are molar gas constants (8.314 KJ) and absolute temperature in Kelvins (285K) respectively. The Gabon constant (K_G) was computed using the relation; $K_G = PBC^K / ECEC$ (Evangelou and Karanthansis, 1986) and signifies the affinity with which K is held in the presence of Ca and Mg in the soil.

Statistical Analysis

Data generated for K forms and Q/I parameters were subjected to analysis of variance and means separated using LSD at 5% probability level. Inter-correlation amongst K forms and correlation between Q/I parameters with K forms and soil properties as well as K forms with soil properties were determined using correlation analysis. All analyses were computed using Genstat statistical package (Genstat, 2005).

Results and Discussion

Soil Characterization

Mean sand, silt and clay ranged from 806.80-886.80, 25.60-42.60 and 37.60-167.60 g kg^{-1}

respectively with sand fraction better than others (Table 1). Also, whereas distribution of sand fraction was better in the topsoil (0-15 cm), clay in the subsoil (15-30 cm) the silt was irregular between depths. High clay content of the subsoil has been reported and attributed to leaching or illuviation processes (Uzoho and Ironkwe, 2020). Soil Texture varied as sandy, sandy loam and loamy sand but dominantly sandy due to the nature of the parent materials which is Coastal Plain sands (Orajiaka, 1975). Mean soil pH ranged between 4.55-5.14 indicating slight to high acidity (Adaikwu and Ali, 2013) ascribable to intense base leaching by the high tropical rainfall. Soil OM, P, TN, ECEC and exchangeable cations were low consistent with Ultisols of Southeastern Nigeria (Enwezor et al., 1990). Also, using the scale of < 0.13 , $0.13-0.1$ and $> 0.31 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$ for low, medium and high K proposed by Unambah-Oparah (1985), the soils were low in K. Generally, soil OM and nutrients (N, P, Ca, Mg and K) were better in the topsoil due to high litter fall and accumulation. Trends in nutrient distribution followed similar pattern as the OM due probably to their existence in the organic form thus supporting the claim that fertility of tropical soils is dependent on their organic matter content (Uzoho and Ironkwe, 2020).

Potassium Forms

Mean soil potassium fractions ranged from 10.83-41.11, 5.94-36.32, 1.04-6.85, 4.07-14.17, 4.90-17.31 and $0.79-3.42 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$ for total, structural, non-exchangeable, exchangeable, available and solution K respectively (Table 2). Also, mean concentration of all the K fractions were significantly (LSD 0.05) better and lower in Oil Palm and Sycamore land-uses. Increased K fertilization of the oil palm land-use could be responsible for its high K content. Averaged over land-uses and soil depths, K forms decreased in the order total $>$ structural $>$ available $>$ exchangeable $>$ non-exchangeable $>$ solution K. In a study of some Bagdad soils, Al-Hamandi et al. (2019) obtained a decreasing sequence of total $>$ exchangeable $>$ non-exchangeable $>$ solution K. The low content of solution K in the soil has been ascribed to its high solubility and ease of loss through microbial/plant root uptake and leaching by high tropical rainfall. Whereas, total and structural K forms were better in subsoil depths of cassava and oil palm, all other fractions were better in topsoil of the land-uses probably due high organic matter contents.

There was significant ($P < 0.05$) inter-correlation amongst the K forms (Table 3). Also, all K forms were strongly correlated with soil pH whereas only available, exchangeable and non-exchangeable were with silt. There was no significant correlation between clay, OM and ECEC with K forms.

Equilibrium K, Ca, Mg and K Quantity and Intensity Factors

Potassium, Ca and Mg in equilibrium solution varied with added K, with mean contents better in the topsoil depth (Table 4). Averaged over soil depths, mean K was better in oil palm while Ca and Mg were in cassava land-uses.

Averaged over soil depths and land-uses types, labile K pool ($\pm \Delta K$) or K quantity factor (Q) increased with added K. with trends being a decreasing order of sycamore (10.77) $>$ plantain (8.42) $>$ oil palm (8.35) $>$ cassava ($8.34 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) and with sycamore land-use better than the others. This variation in quantity factor (index of soil K reserve of non exchangeable K) indicates the extent of K adsorption capacity of the soils (Panda and Patra, 2018). Equally, averaged over land-uses, mean contents were better in the subsoil depths probably due to its high clay content. It has been reported that clay soils have high sorption capacities due to their large surface area and negative charges (Uzoho and Oti, 2005). Its mean range of $8.34-10.77 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$ was better values reported by Yawson et al. (2011).

Table 1. *Physicochemical Properties of Soils of various Land-uses Studied*

Land-use	Soil Depth	Sand	Silt	Clay	OM	TN	pH	P	Ca	Mg	K	Na	ECEC	TC
	Cm	g kg ⁻¹						mg kg ⁻¹	cmol kg ⁻¹					
Oil Palm	0-15	836.8	60	10.32	0.93	0.83	5.85	1.72	4.4	5.8	0.04	0.04	9.47	LS
	15-30	796.8	25.6	177.6	0.55	0.78	4.96	1.33	3.6	1.6	0.02	0.04	6.08	SL
	Mean	816.8	42.8	167.6	0.74	0.81	5.14	1.53	4	3.7	0.03	0.04	7.78	SL
Cassava	0-15	896.8	45.6	57.6	1.93	1.49	4.68	2.31	4.4	7.5	0.04	0.02	11.73	S
	15-30	876.8	45.6	77.6	1.1	1.25	4.42	1.72	4.2	0.04	0.02	0.02	4.85	S
	Mean	886.8	45.6	67.6	1.5	1.37	4.55	2.02	4.3	4	0.03	0.02	8.29	S
Plantain	0-15	976.8	5.6	17.6	0.83	1.14	5	4.52	3.6	3.1	0.01	0.01	4.61	S
	15-30	896.8	65.6	37.6	0.79	0.99	4.52	3.66	1.5	0.5	0.01	0.01	4.12	S
	Mean	936.8	35.6	27.6	0.81	1.02	4.76	4.09	2.55	1.8	0.01	0.01	4.37	S
Sycamore	0-15	816.8	25.6	157.6	1.38	1.27	4.8	1.7	6.5	1.7	0.01	0.01	7.2	SL
	15-30	796.8	25.6	177.6	1.2	1.25	4.77	1.26	5.5	0.5	0.01	0.01	7.02	SL
	Mean	806.8	25.6	167.6	1.29	1.26	4.75	1.45	6	1.1	0.01	0.01	7.11	SL

OM=organic matter, TN=total nitrogen, LS = Loamy sand, SL - Sandy loam and S = Sand, TC=Textural class

Table 2. *Potassium Forms in the Studied Soils*

Land-use	Soil depth	Total K	Struct. K	Non-exch. K	Exch K	Avail. K	Sol. K
	Cm	cmol kg ⁻¹					
Oil Palm	0-15	35.66	28.83	9.00	16.78	19.83	3.05
	15-30	46.56	43.56	4.77	11.55	14.79	3.42
	Mean	41.11	36.32	6.85	14.17	17.31	3.15
Cassava	0-15	20.33	11.97	3.62	7.44	8.35	0.91
	15-30	30.81	18.08	2.35	14.73	15.73	1.00
	Mean	25.57	15.03	2.99	11.09	12.04	0.96
Plantain	0-15	15.65	8.96	2.27	5.05	6.69	1.64
	15-30	10.09	5.67	1.25	4.27	4.42	0.15
	Mean	12.87	7.32	1.76	4.66	5.56	0.90
Sycamore	0-15	11.40	6.32	1.64	4.00	4.88	0.88
	15-30	10.26	5.32	0.44	4.14	4.91	0.77
	Mean	10.83	5.94	1.04	4.07	4.90	0.79
Fact A (LSD _{0.05})		5.62	5.66	1.12	2.13	2.46	0.48
Fact B (LSD _{0.05})		3.98	4.01	0.79	1.51	1.74	0.34
Fact A x B(LSD _{0.05})		7.95	8.01	1.59	3.02	3.48	0.68

Struct. = Structural, exch. = exchangeable, avail. = available and sol. = solution

At low or zero K addition, the lowest and best $\pm \Delta K$ were in subsoil of cassava (-10.06) and topsoil of sycamore (-2.22) land-uses respectively while the lowest and best at highest K addition (30mmol L⁻¹) were in topsoil depths of cassava (21.45) and plantain (28.70 cmol kg⁻¹) land-uses respectively. Difference between the lowest $\pm \Delta K$ at low and high K additions was 31.51 while that between the highest at low and high K additions was 30.92cmol kg⁻¹. These

values were high relative to those of others (Patra et al., 2007; Panda and Patra, 2018) indicative of moderate to high fixation of the added K. The K activity ratio (AR_e^K) varied with added K with means ranging from 2.07-2.80 mol L⁻¹)^{-1/2} that was better in oil palm land-use and topsoil depths. This range was high relative to representative Ghanaian soil series (Yawson et al., 2011). The AR_e^K provides a satisfactory estimate of K availability in soils with variability due to differences in K of the equilibrating solutions, period of equilibration and Ca²⁺ or/and Mg²⁺ contents of soil mineralogy (Yawson et al., 2011). The least and best intensities at low K addition were in oil palm (2.00) and plantain (3.40) while that at the largest K addition were in sycamore (1.39) and cassava (3.17 mol L⁻¹)^{1/2} x 10⁻³ land-uses respectively.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix of K Forms and Selected Soil Properties

	Total K	Struct. K	Non-Exch K	Exch. K	Avail. K	Sol. K	ECEC	OM	pH
Struct. K	0.97**								
Non-Exch. K	0.76**	0.74**							
Exch. K	0.87**	0.77**	0.81**						
Avail. K	0.91**	0.83**	0.85**	0.99**					
Sol. K	0.88**	0.92**	0.82**	0.70**	0.78**				
ECEC	0.34	0.27	0.56**	0.39	0.4	0.33			
OM	-0.04	-0.18	0.05	0.08	0.04	-0.17	0.81**		
pH	0.52*	0.43*	0.54**	0.53**	0.56**	0.53**	0.66**	0.49*	
Clay	0.18	0.23	-0.23	-0.08	-0.04	0.15	0.16	0.2	0.23
Silt	0.28	0.19	0.44*	0.51*	0.45*	0.04	0.43*	0.32	0.46*

Struct. = Structural, *Exch.* = Exchange, *Avail.* = Available and *Sol.* = Solution

The difference between the lowest K at the low and high application rates was -0.64 while that at high rates was -0.24 mol L⁻¹)^{1/2} x 10⁻³ with the later higher than the former. These values were low suggesting poor intensities probably due to high fixation of added K.

Potassium Quantity/Intensity Isotherms

Potassium Q/I isotherms varied with land-uses and soil depths (fig 1). The quantity factors (Q) increased with increasing activity ratios (AR_e^K) resulting to increased upper linear region at moderate and high AR_e^K and a curvilinear shape at low concentrations. Similar observation has been reported (Panda and Patra, 2018; Biliias and Barbayiannis 2019; Al-Hahamdi et al., 2019) and could be due to differences in sorption and availability of K. According to Dutta and Joshi (1990), the linear upper portion of the isotherm was associated with exchange K on planar sites and the lower with edge and interlattice K and with later more tightly held than the former. Different K availability or Q/I parameters obtained from the isotherms were presented in Table 5 and included:

Potassium Equilibrium Activity Ratio (AR_e^{ok})

Mean K equilibrium activity ratio (AR_e^{ok}) ranged from 1.16-2.03 Mol L^{-1/2} x 10⁻³ with oil palm (2.03) and sycamore (1.16 Mol L^{-1/2}) x 10⁻³] significantly higher and lower respectively than other land-uses (Table 5).

Table 4. Equilibrium K, Ca, Mg and K Activity ratio and Changes with Added K in Studied Soils

Added K (mmols L ⁻¹)	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	Mean
Land-use/Soil Depth	Oil Palm (0-15 cm)-Soil 1							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.25	5.2	5.55	8.01	10	10.02	6.55	7.08
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.91	3.28	4.01	4.44	3.43	5.45	4.18	3.95
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.61	2.11	3.44	2	1.12	3.28	2.4	2.42
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	2	2.24	2.03	3.6	4.27	3.4	2.63	2.88
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-4.25	-0.2	4.45	6.99	10	14.98	23.45	7.92
	Oil Palm (15-30 cm)- Soil 2							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.39	5.31	6.03	6.03	8.56	8.22	5.01	6.22
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	3.08	3	4.2	3.28	2.87	4.65	3.97	3.58
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.75	2.22	2.06	1.98	1	2.27	2.93	2.03
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	2	2.32	2.41	2.63	4.41	3.12	2.07	2.71
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-4.39	-0.31	3.97	8.97	11.44	16.78	24.99	8.78
	Cassava (0-15cm)- Soil 3							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	6.73	6	5.5	4.51	5.7	9.43	8.55	6.63
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.4	4.28	3.11	5.45	3	5.87	5.44	4.51
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.08	3.48	2.56	3.48	2.11	3.5	3.11	2.9
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	2.64	2.63	2.3	2.09	3.21	3.1	3.24	2.74
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-6.73	-1	4.5	10.49	14.3	15.57	21.45	8.37
	Cassava (15-30cm)- Soil 4							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	10.06	4.23	4.7	3.34	8.02	8.02	7.51	6.55
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	5	5.42	3.88	3.99	0.98	4	5.3	4.37
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.44	3.88	1.16	2.66	3.66	2.77	2.98	2.79
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	3.7	1.47	2.13	2.12	3.11	3.12	3.09	2.68
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-10.06	0.77	5.3	10.66	11.98	16.98	22.49	8.3
	Plantain (0-15cm)- Soil 5							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	7	7	4	7	3.76	6.4	4.3	5.64
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.1	4.98	2.1	5.86	2.7	4.58	3.8	4.02
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.89	2.58	1.65	4.6	4	3.99	2.08	2.97
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	3.6	3.45	2.1	2.24	1.52	2.56	2.13	2.51
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-7	-2	6	8	16.24	18.6	28.7	7
Land-use/Soil Depth	Plantain (15 -30 cm)- Soil 6							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	7	3.33	5.4	5.1	4.34	5.33	5.58	5.15
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	3.01	3.56	3.48	4.66	4.2	3.36	3.67	3.71
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.98	1.98	2	3.88	3.2	2.44	1.89	2.47
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	3.2	1.41	2.3	2.51	2.15	2.21	2.46	2.32
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-7.1	1.67	4.6	9.9	15.66	19.67	24.42	9.83
	Sycamore (0-15cm)- Soil 7							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.22	4.43	6.41	4.39	3.4	4.34	3.88	4.01
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.2	4.44	3.02	3.86	2.36	3.15	4.98	3.72
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.11	2.8	2.96	22.11	3.06	1.28	2.57	2.41
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	1.13	2.53	3.21	2.16	1.5	2.06	1.41	2
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-2.22	0.57	3.59	10.61	10.6	21.66	26.12	10.99
	Sycamore (15-30 cm)- Soil 8							
K (cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.44	2.11	4.8	3.9	4.51	3.85	2.65	3.75
Ca(cmol kg ⁻¹)	5.14	3.94	4.3	2.98	1.97	2.3	2.4	3.29
Mg(cmol kg ⁻¹)	22.04	2.7	3.4	1.88	4.82	1.94	1.98	2.68
Activity Ratio(mol L ⁻¹)	2.15	1.28	2.37	2.8	2.3	2.7	1.36	2.14
Adsorbed K(cmol ⁻¹ mol L ⁻¹)	-4.44	2.89	5.2	11.1	15.49	16.15	27.37	10.54

Also, topsoil content was distinctly better than the subsoil. This range was low relative to values reported for alluvial soils of varying cropping systems in India (Lalitha and Dhakshinomoorthy, 2015), coastal eastern India soils (Panda and Patra, 2018) but high compared to representative Ghananian soil series (Yawson et al., 2011).

Table 5. Potassium Quantity/Intensity Parameters of Studied Soils

Land-use	Soil Depths	AR_e^{ok}	K_L	K_o	K_x	PBC^{ok}	K Pot.	K_G	ΔG	K Sat.
	Cm	$MolL^{-1/2} \times 10^{-3}$				$cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$		$Lmol^{-1/2}$	$KJ\ mol\ L^{-1}$	%
Oil Palm	0-15	1.9	10	4.5	6	6	27	0.63	1425.55	0.66
	15-30	2.15	21	3.75	17.25	6.74	25.28	1.11	1700.09	0.21
	Mean	2.03	15.75	4.13	11.63	6.37	26.14	0.82	1562.82	0.44
Cassava	0-15	2.15	20.13	7.25	12.88	9.27	67.35	0.79	1658.88	0.17
	15-30	1.45	15	5	10	8	40	1.65	825.24	0.82
	Mean	1.8	17.57	6.13	11.44	8.64	53.68	1.04	1242.06	0.5
Plantain	0-15	1.49	10	4.25	5.75	7.6	32.3	1.65	885.67	0.24
	15-30	1.39	8.5	3	5.5	8.42	25.26	2.04	731.38	0.22
	Mean	1.44	9.25	3.63	5.63	8.01	28.78	1.83	808.53	0.23
Sycamore	0-15	1.2	15	5.5	9.5	12.02	66.11	1.67	404.93	0.14
	15-30	1.12	20.5	5.5	15	7.6	41.8	1.08	251.71	0.14
	Mean	1.16	17.75	5.5	12.25	9.81	53.96	1.38	328.32	0.14
Fact A (LSD _{0.05})		0.31	3.26	0.99	2.47	1.47	10.19	0.26	288.69	0.11
Fact B (LSD _{0.05})		0.22	2.31	0.7	1.75	1.04	7.2	0.18	204.14	0.08
Fact A x B(LSD _{0.05})		0.44	4.61	1.4	3.5	2.08	14.4	0.36	408.27	0.16

Pot.= Potential and Sat. = Saturation

The AR_e^{ok} is a measure of immediate plant K^+ availability, with variations due to differences in K^+ ionic strength and with higher values associated with high ionic strength and greater K availability to plants relative to Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} (Panda and Patra, 2018). It could also be due to differences in K^+ concentration in equilibrium solution, equilibration period, Ca^+ and/ Mg^+ contents and differences in soil mineralogy (Yawson et al., 2011; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). It has been reported that AR_e^{ok} is high in soils with high exchangeable and non exchangeable K^+ (Jagadeesh et al., 2005). Low values in soils has been ascribed to large number of specific sites which could fix K while high values has been suggested to be due to adsorbed K primarily held in planar sites with greater K^+ supply intensity and thus more K for plant absorption (Abaslou and Abtahi, 2008; Panda and Patra, 2018). Generally, values obtained for the studied soils were greater than a threshold value of $AR_e^{ok} \geq 0.001\ MI^{-1})^{1/2}$ (Al-Hamandi et al., 2019) or $0.002\ MI^{-1})^{1/2}$ known to be non limiting to plant growth (Sharma,et al., 2012) thus indicating good ability for K supply in solution. Soil AR_e^{ok} was significantly ($P < 0.05$) correlated with K_L , K_x , K_o , PBC^{ok} and ΔG but not K_G and K_{sat} (Table 6).

Table 6. Inter-correlation between Q/I Parameters and the parameters with selected Soil Properties

	AR _e ^{ok}	K _L	K _o	K _x	PBC ^{ok}	K Pot	K _G	ΔG	Ksat	ECEC	OM	pH
K _L	0.61 ^{**}											
K _o	0.60 ^{**}	0.79 ^{**}										
K _x	0.56 ^{**}	0.98 ^{**}	0.59 ^{**}									
PBC ^{ok}	0.42 [*]	0.54 ^{**}	0.75 ^{**}	0.4								
K Pot	0.36	0.62 ^{**}	0.90 ^{**}	0.45 [*]	0.85 ^{**}							
K _G	0.11	0.1	0.16	0.05	0.68 ^{**}	0.25						
ΔG	0.93 ^{**}	0.41 [*]	0.36	0.4	0.11	0.14	-0.14					
K sat	0.31	-0.03	0.16	-0.07	0.01	-0.06	0.13	0.28				
ECEC	-0.11	-0.07	0	-0.08	-0.01	-0.01	0.01	-0.15	0.14			
OM	-0.09	0.04	0.09	0.02	0.07	0.09	0.01	-0.15	0.03	0.81 ^{**}		
pH	-0.14	-0.13	-0.2	-0.1	-0.16	-0.21	0.03	-0.11	0.06	0.66 ^{**}	0.49 [*]	
Clay	0.13	0.17	0.3	0.09	0.4	0.28	0.46 [*]	-0.04	-0.15	0.16	0.2	0.23
Silt	0.21	0.19	-0.07	0.27	-0.24	-0.23	-0.24	0.26	0.3	0.43 [*]	0.32	0.46 [*]

Others have reported significant relationship between AR_e^{ok} with K_x, K_o, ΔG and PBC^{ok} (Panda and Patra, 2018). Also, significant relationship has been reported between AR_e^{ok} and ΔG (Yawson et al., 2011). There was no distinct correlation between AR_e^{ok} silt, clay, pH, OM and ECEC. Similar relationship has been reported between AR_e^{ok} with pH and clay (Diatta et al., 2006; Absalou and Abathi, 2008; Yawson et al., 2011).

Fig. 1. Potassium quantity and intensity Isotherms of Soils of different Land-uses

Labile K (K_L)

Labile K represents plants readily available K that is capable of ion exchange during periods of equilibration between soil solids and soil solution (Lin, 2010). Its mean content ranged from 9.25-17.75 cmol kg^{-1} , with sycamore and plantain better and lower respectively than other land-uses. Compared to ranges reported by others (Panda and Patra 2018; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019), that for these soils was high. It has been reported that high labile K values in soils is indicative of greater K release into solution from larger pool of soil K (Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). Averaged over land-uses, subsoil (16.25) content was better than the topsoil soil depth (13.78 cmol kg^{-1}) with the variation probably due to differences in soil characteristics and K sorption capacity. There was significant correlation between K_L with AR_e^{ok} , K_x , K_o , ΔG and PBC^{ok} and not K_G and K_{sat} . Also, K_L was not distinctly correlated with selected soil properties especially silt, clay, pH, OM and ECEC. Significant correlation has also been reported between K_L and K_x but not with soil properties (Panda and Patra, 2018). Poor relationship between K_L and soil properties could be due to non dependence of labile K on soil attributes contrary to earlier observations of its relationship with soil clay, ECEC, non-exchangeable K and loosely bound K^+ ions in exchange sites (Jagadeesh et al., 2005; Samadi, 2006). Values for the Soil K_L was better than NH_4OAc extractable K indicating that K release from the soil could be through diffusion and solubility process rather than ion exchange reactions (Abaslou and Abtahi 2008; Panda and Patra, 2018).

Non Specific Site K (K_o)

Mean K_o ranged from 3.63-6.13 cmol kg^{-1} about 34.53-39.24% of K_L with cassava (6.13) and plantain (3.63 $\text{cmol kg}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$) significantly (LSD 0.05) higher and lower respectively than other land-uses (Table 5). This range was high relative to values reported for alluvial soils (Dhillon, 1986), representative Ghanaian soil series (Yawson et al., 2011) and coastal eastern soils of India (Panda and Patra, 2018). Also, averaged over land-uses topsoil (5.38) was distinctly better than subsoil soil depths (3.56 cmol kg^{-1}). The high values for the soils signify K adsorption to non specific sites (Abaslou and Abtahi 2008). Non specific K constitutes the immediate available K that is held on non-specific planar sites of the soil. Its concentration was significantly correlated with K_x , PBC^{ok} and K potential but not with K_{sat} , K_G and ΔG (Table 6). It was also not distinctly correlated with all soil properties. Similar observation has been noted between K_o with K_x and PBC^{ok} but not silt, clay and OM as in the studied soils (Panda and Patra, 2018).

Specific Site K (K_x)

Specific site K is a measure of the capacity of K to be held with high or specific affinity on wedge and edge mineral sites. Its mean range for the studied soils was between 5.63-12.25 cmol kg^{-1} , with sycamore (12.25) and plantain (5.63 cmol kg^{-1}) distinctly higher and lower respectively than other land-uses. Compared to ranges for other soils (Patra et al., 2007; Panda and Patra, 2018) that for studied soils was high. Also, averaged over land-uses, it was better in the sub (11.94) than topsoil (8.53 cmol kg^{-1}) depths, with high subsoil content probably due to the large clay content. Specific site K was significantly correlated with AR_e^{ok} , K_L , K_o and K potential but not PBC^{ok} , K_{sat} , K_G and ΔG . It was also not distinctly correlated with ECEC, OM, pH, silt and

clay. Significant correlation has been reported between K_x with AR_e^{ok} , K_L , PBC^{ok} , ΔG and K_{sat} and none with silt, clay and OM (Panda and Patra, 2018). Equally, significant correlation has been obtained between K_x with K_L (Patra et al., 2007) and PBC^{ok} (Diatta et al., 2006).

Potential Buffering Capacity (PBC^{ok})

Mean potential buffering capacity ranged from 6.37-9.81 $cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$ being better in sycamore (9.81) and lower in oil palm (6.37 $cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$) land-uses. It was also better in the topsoil (8.72) than subsoil (7.69 $cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$). Variation in soil PBC^{ok} has been noted to be due to difference in soil management practice, cropping pattern (Yawson et al., 2011) and clay mineralogy (Diatta et al., 2006). Studies indicate that high PBC^{ok} signifies good K availability in soil solution while the reverse suggests a need for frequent K fertilization (Panda and Patra, 2018, Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). According to Abaslou and Abathi (2008), removal of adsorbed K from non-specific planar sites via plant uptake promotes soil buffering capacity, thus suggesting that higher energy surfaces become involved as cropping become intensified. The PBC^{ok} is a measure of the ability of soil to maintain the solution K concentration against depletion by plant uptake and leaching losses or the resistance to change in K-potential in soil solution (Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). The range for the studied soils was low relative to values for coastal soils of eastern India (Panda and Patra, 2018) but high compared to alluvial soils of Bagdad (Al-Hamandi et al. (2019) . According to Hamed and Amin (2017), PBC^{ok} has been classified into very low (< 20), medium (20-200) and very high ($> 200\ cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$) thus suggesting a very low PBC^{ok} for the studied soils and a poor ability to maintain solution K as it is depleted through leaching and uptake. Panda and Patra (2018) suggested the need for frequent K fertilization to maintain optimum crop yield in soils with low PBC^{ok} . Low soil PBC^{ok} has been noted to be due to high a K saturation (Munn and Mclean, 1975) while the reverse could be associated with low soil K saturation and pH and thus suggesting a high potential for solution K replenishment (Arnold, 1978). Hence, the high K saturation of most land-uses accounted for the low PBC^{ok} of the soils. Besides $-\Delta G$, K_x , and silt, clay, pH, OM and ECEC, PBC^{ok} correlated significantly ($P < 0.05$) with AR_e^{ok} , K_L , K_o , K_{sat} and K_G . Others have reported significant correlation between PBC^{ok} with AR_e^{ok} , K_o and K_{sat} (Panda and Patra, 2018). Also, similar relationship has been reported between PBC^{ok} and AR_e^{ok} (Jagadeesh et al., 2005). Equally, non significant relationship has been noted between PBC^{ok} and the soil properties (Panda and Patra, 2018).

Potassium Potential (K_{pot})

Potassium potential is an index of K availability and measures Q/I in a single parameter. Its mean range was 26.14-53.96 $cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$ with sycamore (53.96) and cassava (26.14) land-uses significantly (LSD 0.05) higher and lower respectively. Also, mean topsoil (48.19) was better than subsoil depths (33.09 $cmol\ kg^{-1}(mol\ L^{-1})^{-1/2}$). Compared to the range reported by Yawson et al. (2011) and Panda and Patra (2018) the range for the studied soils was high. It has been indicated that soils with high K potential have higher K_o and PBC^{ok} and thus a tendency for more K release from the planar sites at equilibrium (Diatta et al., 2006; Abaslou and Abathi, 2008). Besides K_{sat} , K_G and ΔG correlation between K potential with K_L , K_x , K_o and AR_e^{ok} was significant. Also, there was no significant correlation between K potential with silt, clay, pH, OM

and ECEC. Similar relationship has been reported between K potential with soil properties (Panda and Patra, 2018).

Gapon Selectivity Coefficient (K_G)

The Gapon selectivity coefficient (K_G) is a measure of the relative affinity of the soil for K in the presence of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} at soil solid and solution equilibrium (Samadi, 2006; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). Its mean range was $0.82\text{-}1.83 \text{ Lmol}^{-1})^{1/2}$ with cassava (0.82) and plantain ($1.83\text{Lmol}^{-1})^{1/2}$) significantly lower and higher respectively than other land-uses. This range is high relative to a value of $0.02\text{-}0.07 \text{ Lmol}^{-1})^{1/2}$ for alluvial Bagdad soils (Al-Hamandi et al., 2018) but low relative to that of $4.2\text{-}12.99 \text{ Lmol}^{-1})^{1/2}$ for some Iranian soils (Abaslou and Abathi, 2008). Changes in soil K_G has been ascribed to the levels of exchangeable Ca and Mg (Bernard and Kocialkowski 2006). Also, its subsoil (1.47) content was better than the topsoil ($1.19\text{Lmol}^{-1})^{1/2}$). Selectivity of K over Ca and Mg has been attributed to the preferential attraction of K to both Ca and Mg at some planar sites of soil colloid when $\text{Ca} + \text{Mg} = \text{ECEC}$ (Poonia and Niederbudde, 1990). There was significant correlation between K_G and PBC^{ok} but not with other Q/I parameters. Besides, clay ($r = 0.46$), correlation between K_G and soil properties (silt, pH, OM and ECEC) was also not significant. Its significant relationship with clay has also been reported (Absalou and Abathi, 2008).

Free Energy of Potassium Replacement ($-\Delta G$)

Mean $-\Delta G$ ranged from $328.32\text{-}1562.82 \text{ KJ mol L}^{-1}$ with oil palm (1562.82) and sycamore having the best ($1562.82 \text{ KJ mol L}^{-1}$) and least ($328.32\text{KJ mol L}^{-1}$) values respectively. This range was low compared to that of $1937\text{-}3236 \text{ cal e}^{-1}$ by Dutta and Joshi (1990) but high relative to values for hilly and coastal soils, acid inceptisols, coastal eastern Indian soils and alluvial soils of Bagdad (Jagadeesh et al., 2005; Patra et al., 2007; Panda and Patra, 2018; Al-Hamandi et al., 2019). Mean topsoil ΔG (1093.76) was also better than the subsoil ($877.11 \text{ KJ mol L}^{-1}$). Availability of soil K has been classified sufficient at $-\Delta G < -0.48$, medium (-0.60 to -0.70) and deficient (-0.84 to $-0.96 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$) (Bilias and Barbayiannis, 2019) while Zhang et al. (2011) indicated a value of 14 KJ mol^{-1} as none limiting to plant growth and development and Sharma et al. (2012) with $-\Delta G$ greater than 14.67 as deficient. Also, according to Woodruff (1955), soils with $\Delta G < -3500 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$ or $< 3800 \text{ cal e}^{-1}$) could be K deficient and plants respond to K fertilization while those between -3000 and $-2500 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$ are optimum with plants not responding to K fertilization. This shows that all the soils studied could be K deficient with plant response to K fertilization. The ΔG correlated distinctly with K_L and AR_e^{ok} but not with other Q/I parameters. Other workers have reported significant correlation between ΔG and AR_e^{ok} (Abaslou and Abtahi 2008; Panda and Patra, 2018). There was also no significant correlation with all soil properties, thus suggesting the dependence on the soil mineralogical composition.

Potassium Saturation

Mean K saturation decreased in the order cassava (0.50) > oil palm (0.44) > plantain (0.23) > sycamore (0.14%) with a range of 0.14-0.50% and significantly better and lower in cassava (0.50) and sycamore (0.14 %) land-uses respectively. Compared to values reported by Panda and Patra (2018), the range for this soil was low probably due to the high K fixation or leaching losses. This thus implies a low

soil K status since K saturation is useful estimating soil K mobility or status (Yawson et al., 2011). Mean subsoil (0.35 %) content was better than the topsoil (0.30) probably due to illuviation with percolating water. Potassium saturation was not significantly correlated with K forms and soil properties suggesting the impact of soil mineralogy on its concentration.

Conclusion

Soils were coarse textured, acidic, low OM, ECEC and nutrient content and thus poor in fertility. Potassium forms varied with soil depths and land-uses and thus decreased in the order total > structural > available > exchangeable > non-exchangeable > solution K averaged over depths and land-uses. Correlation amongst K forms and between exchangeable, non-exchangeable and available K with silt and all K forms with soil pH were significant. Soil K Q/I parameters (K_{sat} , K_G , ΔG , K potential, K_L , K_x , K_o and AR_e^{ok}) varied with land-uses, with most being deficient in K availability. Most K Q/I parameters were influenced by soil properties and K forms. In general, K Q/I concept could be useful for estimation of soil K status and sustained K fertilizer management.

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